

North American Academic
Research | Volume 5 | Issue 2 |
February 2022 | Monthly Journal
by TWASP, USA | Impact Factor:
3.75 (2021)

North American Academic Research

Monthly Journal by **The World
Association of Scientists & Professionals**
TWASP, United States

Integration of Supply Chain Management in Tunisian Small Scale Farmers

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Accepted February 16,2022

Published February 24,2022

Copyright: © The Author(s); **Conflicts of Interest:** There are no conflicts to declare.

*Corresponding Author: Yuan Yanhong

Funding: None

How to cite this article: Firas Trabelsi, Yuan Yanhong (2022). Integration of Supply Chain Management in Tunisian Small Scale Farmers. *North American Academic Research*, 5(2), 116-126. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6260864>

ABSTRACT

The goal of this article is to show how supply chain management knowledge may be acquired and incorporated in a small or medium-sized organization to improve existing business efficiency while also creating new business opportunities. The case study method has been selected. The thesis' findings corroborate the traits and challenges identified in earlier SME literature. Furthermore, this research adds to the body of knowledge by delving into the development process of supply chain management adoption in small and medium-sized businesses. It is proposed that the solution be adjusted to the demands of a small or medium-sized business to account for time and resource restrictions. Continuous improvement is described in the thesis as a method for managing change and embedding collaboration in a small business. Furthermore, it has been demonstrated that internal integration must be established before external integration and collaboration may take place, even in small businesses.

Keywords

SMEs, SCM, Tunisia, Small Scale Farmers

1. Introduction

1.1 Aim of The Research

To determine how supply chain management knowledge may be created and entrenched in a SME to improve present business efficiency while also creating a new business opportunity.

1.2 Research Background

Tunisia has been developing toward a market economy in recent years, and more Tunisian businesses are attempting to improve their management to compete in the tough market. Nowadays, market competitiveness has shifted to an era of competition centered on the supply chain. Many businesses see supply chain management and optimization as a critical component of improving their competitiveness. Many businesses are grappling with how to better build supply chain awareness, optimize the industrial supply chain, and increase supply chain management and operational effectiveness.

1.3 Overview to Topic

Supply chain partners have become a growing source of competitive advantage for businesses [1]. Relational rent is defined as "a supernormal profit jointly generated in an exchange relationship that cannot be generated by either firm in isolation or can only be created through the joint idiosyncratic contributions of the specific alliance partners" [2]. SCM is a method of managing inter-firm relationships with the goal of generating relational rents and competitive advantage. Except for a few recent works [3], most studies on partnerships in supply chain management focus on large firms. The benefits of supply chain partnerships for SMEs have been a source of debate in contemporary research on SMEs. The debate centers on the extent to which supply chain alliances can truly assist SMEs. There is data that demonstrates how supply chain alliances can help SMEs. High-tech SMEs, even more than larger enterprises, require external skills and technological expertise to establish their own inventive capabilities and reach their markets [4]. In a survey of Chinese manufacturing SMEs, for example, it was discovered that inter-firm cooperation has the most positive impact on SMEs' creative performance. As a result, partnerships give SMEs access to a wide range of external expertise, can assist them in solving business difficulties, and allow them to participate in learning networks. However, there is some data to suggest that supply chain alliances do not assist SMEs. According to a study, there is a negative relationship between SCM and the accompanying partnerships, which reduces the flexibility of SMEs due to the management, control, and support requirements connected with these partnerships.

2. Literature

2.1 Concept of Supply Chain

The supply chain, also known as the demand chain, is a network chain structure established by upstream and downstream firms involved in supplying products or services to end-users in the production and circulation process. The needs of customers guide the entire supply chain. It begins with raw material suppliers, continues with product creation and design, raw material supply, production, warehousing and transportation, wholesale, retail, and other links, and concludes with various commercial activities to provide products to end consumers. Supply chain optimization aims to establish a strategic partnership among suppliers, manufacturers, distributors, retailers, and users, minimize internal consumption and waste, and optimize the overall efficiency and benefit of the supply chain by planning, organizing, coordinating, and controlling logistics, information flow, capital flow, value flow, and workflow in the supply chain. When

global economic integration and outsourcing strategies are widely adopted to improve companies' core competitiveness, the business community is increasingly favoring supply chain as a new model of successful rivalry among enterprises.

2.2 Evolution of SCM

To have the option to assess the present status of SCM as a rule, however particularly in SMEs for section two and three of this section, it is advantageous to investigate the roots and starting points of SCM [6]. The section beneath momentarily rebuilds the set of experiences and improvement of SCM.

The improvement of SCM is likewise intertwined with the advancement of planned operations. By and large, strategic policies have not seen significant changes since the modern insurgency. Just when the market power moved from venders to purchasers, rehearses for serving clients were upgraded [7]. Likewise, during the 1960s strategic approaches changed from value-based to social [8]. Actual dissemination was conceived, which is the administration of exercises worried about providing clients.

3. Methodology

3.1 Research Philosophy

Perspective and research choice are influenced by research philosophy or philosophical preferences. 1-1 diagram. Academic research attempts to add to and develop knowledge, thus the researcher must consider the two concerns above. Positivism, idealism, interpretivism, constructionism, realism, and pragmatism are some of the schools of thought or research paradigms. In Table 1-1, they are briefly compared.

Table 1-1: Thought Methodology

School of thought	Description
Positivism	Hypotheses basis of existing ideas have been tested.
Idealism	The priority moves away from what is occurring "out there" is towards what is going on in the researcher's head.
Interpretivism	Look for new social rules that people use to make sense of their surroundings.
Constructionism	Fascinated by how social interactions influence people's perceptions of reality.
Realism	Aspects of positivist and interpretivist positions are combined. Real structures exist regardless of human

	consciousness, but knowledge is constructed through social interaction.
Pragmatism	emphasizes the social construction of logic and sense, as well as the role of conversation in reconciling opposing viewpoints.

Figure 1-1: Research Philosophy

3.2 Case study

Using information and data gathered during research, provide a case study about Tunisian small-scale farmers (SSCF). The overall picture of the SSCF supply chain should become obvious by looking at supply chain structures, supply chain performance, and the business context. The case study also acts as a foundation for the analysis, debate, and recommendation in the following chapter, allowing the researcher to answer the research question of if and how SCM competence can be generated and integrated in SMEs.

4. Small Scale Farmers

4.1 Concept of Supply Chain in Small Scale Farmers

Store network is a utilitarian organization chain structure that interfaces providers, makers, sub dealers, retailers, and end clients into an entire by zeroing in on center undertakings and controlling data stream, strategies, and capital stream, beginning from buying unrefined substances, making moderate items and eventual outcomes, lastly sending items to customers by the business organization.

From the idea of cultivating industry store network, the cultivating business production network initially incorporates the suppliers of different merchandise, and afterward incorporates different undertakings answerable for creation and providers of crude and materials of cultivating. According to the point of view of

clients, the back-finish of the production network of the cultivating business incorporates a wide range of wholesalers, yet additionally retailers. It additionally incorporates a wide range of planned operations ventures occupied with warehousing and transportation. As per the above examination, it is easy for us to draw the accompanying improved on model of the store network of the cultivating business, as displayed in Figure 1-2

Figure 1-2: Simplified model of supply chain in farming industry

4.2 Problems in SSCF

There are not many center undertakings in the inventory network of the limited scale ranchers, and the center job isn't self-evident. Christopher, a well-known American inventory network the board master, brought up: "the opposition in the 21st century is as of now not the opposition between endeavors, yet the opposition between supply chains". The interests of every part in the production network are the aftereffect of the joint activity of every hub endeavor in the production network and different individuals. Production network the board moves the free autonomous venture activity to the in general composed activity of the inventory network, to work on the effectiveness of collaboration.

The greater part of Tunisia's agribusiness ventures are incorporated plans of action, and there are not many sections of the store network. In the U.S. Cultivating SMEs, the division of work in the inventory network is generally fine. These expert organizations give effective re-appropriating administrations to the entire inventory network, simultaneously, it additionally diminishes the creation and administration expenses of the entire inventory network through its near benefits. Many endeavors in Tunisia are excited about the incorporated activity including the entire course of the Farming SMEs. Subsequently, they not just waste restricted assets and debilitate their own benefits, yet in addition dissolve the living space of the partitioned market and breaking point the advancement of expert organizations.

We can change a few conventional working modes. The book bundling, promoting arranging and different substance of the distributing house can help proficient organizations through rethinking, to partition the distributing work and distribute books more precisely, quicker, and monetarily. The accompanying Figure 1-3 is a short depiction of the market fragment providers we need:

Figure 1-3: Small scale farmers segmentation supplier market

5. Optimization

5.1 Optimization of SCM in SSCF

Creation is a necessary piece of the general work of the party and the state. It is a significant field of the party's purposeful publicity and philosophical front. In this way, to fortify the large scale administration of SSCF, we should take advancing the solid improvement of the otherworldly and cultivating industry, complying with the party's authority over the cultivating work, complying with the directing situation on field, and complying to the forward course and predominant place of communist progressed culture as a definitive objective, , government the executives, industry self-control The full scale administration arrangement of autonomous activity of ventures and establishments, fix the connection between the public authority and the market, functional undertakings, public government assistance endeavors and ranchers affiliations, explain the individual assignments and obligations of states, industry affiliations, undertakings and foundations, and guarantee the economical, sound and quick advancement of limited scope ranchers.

5.1.1 Focus on Core Enterprises

Under the foundation of the new rural framework change of fortifying the development of agrarian industrialization and endeavor bunch, the consolidation and revamping among homesteads, dissemination and shipping undertakings establish the pattern of Tunisia's agribusiness framework change. The public authority

ought to additionally advance the most common way of cultivating collectivization, incorporate assets to "fabricate a major boat" through collectivization improvement and concentrated activity, and use market-situated means to construct a modern subject with solid market control. Creation and dissemination ventures need to figure out how to apply capital activity means, for example, An and solid coalition, to understand the quick improvement of big business scale and strength and construct a center endeavor in the inventory network of the Farming SMEs.

There is no control and controlled connection between the hub undertakings of the production network. They meet up altogether for the normal interests. To get the greatest benefit esteem, ventures in store network the board should take on participation procedure and diminish duplicity and lack of bias. The greatest benefit of this execution conspire is that the center undertaking is in the production network and a connection in the inventory network, so it can and will limit the expense of the inventory network and amplify the pay from its own advantages. The model is displayed in Figure 1-4. The store network the board stage given by center undertakings is a public information stage, which advances the trading of big business data in the store network and works with ventures to acknowledge production network the executives. The store network the board stage comprises of three sections: network framework, store network the executives' administrations and specialized help. Deeply, network foundation is the equipment condition, and specialized help is the key.

Figure 1-4: Supply chain core enterprise information management model

5.1.2 Distribute Profit Equally

The advantage conveyance inside the inventory network is the center issue of the store network. In the inventory network of SSCF, each connection of creation, bundling and conveyance gets various benefits. This peculiarity is sensible because it mirrors the worth commitment level of various undertakings or various hubs

in the production network. Nonetheless, assuming the interest appropriation of the production network is excessively unique, it will cause the interest struggle between the ventures at the hubs of the store network and make the interests of endeavors of various hub sorts of contention with the general interests of the inventory network. Measurements show that the general extent of benefit dissemination in the store network is handling represents 10% of the absolute benefit, request getting represents 20% of the all-out benefit, brand represents 30% of the complete benefit, and promoting represents 40% of the all-out benefit. In the connections of creation, bundling, dissemination, and supply in Tunisia's Farming SMEs, the benefit circulation extent is unique in relation to the above broad circumstance. This extent dissemination has caused an irregularity in the upstream and downstream advancement of the store network and impacted the harmless intelligent improvement of the entire production network. The public authority needs to arrange and incorporate social assets as indicated by the asset gift states of various endeavors and reinforce the planned improvement among hub undertakings by sensibly appropriating the benefit extent of every hub venture in the production network, to understand the sound advancement of the store network.

5.1.3 Standard Platform for Small Scale Farmers

To create and keep a fruitful inventory network, the quintessence of data framework requires a consistent connection among ventures and inside endeavors, and that implies interfacing all divisions inside the undertaking to lay out a data framework including showcasing, deals, obtainment, money, appropriation, and interior transportation, and extending to the outside of the venture, including clients, providers Transporters and retailers. Through the common data stage laid out by every hub of the retail store network, retailers share the business data and stock data with upstream undertakings, so they can get a handle on the business circumstance of items continuously, keep the creation synchronized with the market as far as possible, further develop the reaction speed of the entire store network, lastly live up to the assumptions of purchasers. We can lay out an administration data framework as displayed in the Figure 1-5 beneath:

Figure 1-5: Farming SMEs management information system

The objective of the farming data trade standard is to understand the data trade and data partaking in the business to understand the exchange of cross stage data frameworks in a bound together language design. It is the bounden obligation of the equipped government divisions to assemble and further develop the electronic data principles of book items in the Farming SMEs at the earliest opportunity. Since this work can't be finished by a creation, bundling, or dispersion bunch, yet should be finished in the heterogeneous data frameworks of various endeavors in the entire business.

5.2 Information Chain

Make another data chain considering the organization and online business climate. In SCM, data stream assumes a critical part, including feedforward data stream and input data stream. The data stream in these two bearings drives the activity of capital stream and strategies in the inventory network, interfacing the ranchers, packager, center market, retail location and clients.

From the current circumstance of the production network of the homegrown Farming SMEs, a significant number of endeavors have laid out administration data frameworks (MIS), however the greater part of these frameworks is utilized for interior administration, and there is no compelling data stream in the production network. Accept bibliographic data for instance. Ranchers rehash it, specialists and wholesalers rehash it in their own information base, and retail locations should rehash it after buying. The fragmented stockpiling and separate utilization of data not just goal covering capacities and low productivity in the chain, yet additionally cause the constructed data framework to turn into a data island. Consequently, it is important to dig the data dissemination diverts in the inventory network, lay out a brought together data stage, take on

standard information design and normalized archive transmission mode, so the undertakings partaking in the production network can share data, lastly change the data advantage into upper hand.

In this way, in view of the organization and web-based business model, considering completely the improvement elements and industry foundation of the Farming SMEs, we can construct another data chain with the distributing gathering or conveyance bunch as the center endeavor of the entire inventory network. Center undertakings assume the part of association structure change focus, data trade focus and strategies conveyance dispatching focus in the entire production network. In the center endeavor, there is a somewhat huge data network administration focus, which connects with the data frameworks of other hub undertakings in the store network through intranet as displayed in Figure 1-6:

Figure 1-6: Information network structure model of SSCF Supply Chain Based

6. End Notes

6.1 Conclusion

This proposal takes the momentum circumstance of the store network of the limited scale ranchers as the exploration object, dissects the issues existing in the current circumstance of the inventory network of the SSCF, and advances the essential countermeasures to manage these issues. There are numerous issues in the inventory network of the Farming SMEs. This paper centers around the issues, for example, the hazy job of the center undertakings in the store network, the muddled proficient division of work, the absence of providers in the market sections, the unfortunate level of coordination among the ventures in the production network,

and the unfortunate data correspondence among the endeavors. Considering these issues in the inventory network of Farming SMEs, this paper advances a few countermeasures, mostly from the two parts of government and endeavors.

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